

Milestone MS23

Report on evaluation on Msc course modules developed on the base of recommendations from Task 6.3

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Introduction

The task 6.3 “Training and education strategy” demonstrated that current and accessible knowledge and skills did not meet totally the key challenges that farmers and advisors are facing regarding crop diversification. Various gaps of skills and knowledge were addressed and can be grouped in three categories:

1. Understand concepts of diversification and the resulting dynamics of change in farming practices
2. Design under complex and uncertain context
3. Acquire the attitude to act within and have impact on the sociotechnical context

It appears that current training and education programmes still need to uptake concepts, approaches and tools related to crop diversification. DiverIMPACTS provides tools and resources that can be directly mobilized in current teaching programmes and thus upscale future actors of the agrifood system with knowledge and skills needed to meet the challenge of crop diversification.

In order to train and accompany farmers, advisors and all actors of agricultural knowledge systems, a policy brief (https://zenodo.org/record/6801262#.YuJ0Ft86_GI) related to training and education strategy has been produced. This policy brief gathered recommendations at both national and European level to alter and improve processes of teaching, training for all AKIS actors.

Innovative ways (and contents) of teaching the identified skills and knowledge were subsequently tested during the last year of the DiverIMPACTS project in existing MSc courses in ESA (France), SLU (Sweden) and WU (Netherlands). Material and outputs from DiverIMPACTS were mobilized to introduce new contents in these courses.

Table 1: context of implementation of Msc courses on crop diversification based on DI

Structure	Country	MSc program	MSc course	Module hours/duration of the Msc Course	Number of students	Number of credits
Ecole supérieure	France	MSc in Agroecology in plant production	Diversity	9h (8 Nov 2021 – 24 Dec 2021)	29	6

d'agricultures (ESA)						
Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SLU)	Sweden	MSc in Agroecology MSc in Food and Landscape	Agroecology and sustainability of production systems	9h (02 Nov 2021-14 Jan 2022)	35	15
WU	Netherlands	MSc Analysis and Design of Organic Farming Systems		3 continuous weeks (7 June 2021 - 2 July 2021)	60	

Feedbacks from these three experiences of MSc courses were gathered with the aim to (i) identify further improvements in the proposed teaching material and (ii) make evolve the recommendations related to training and education strategy.

These first experiences of implementation of DiverIMPACTS recommendations and outputs in Msc Courses is to be considered as an example to be reproduced and adapted to existing teaching programme, or to get inspired from to create new teaching modules.

Potential changes in current teaching and advisory approaches as well as in their practical contents were identified.

The following table summarizes:

- Those needs identified to foster and implement crop diversification;
- The recommendations proposed to address the needs in terms of knowledge, skills and attitudes to develop;
- Some examples of implementation (from the 3 experiences);
- The role of students;
- Comments or feedbacks.

Table 2: Summary of implemented content derived from DiverIMPACTS outputs, role of students and feedbacks in three MSc programs from ESA (in red), SLU (in green) and WUR (in blue)

Needs to foster and implement crop diversification	How to address the need? knowledge, skills and attitudes to develop		Examples of implementation	Role of students	Comments/feedbacks from students
<p>Understand concepts of diversification and the resulting dynamics of change in farming practices</p>	<p>Learn about</p>	<p>Knowledge mobilized at the agronomic level: Crop diversification strategies (spatial and temporal), features and benefits/trade-offs</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Illustrations of innovative strategies • Identification of the risks associated to crop diversification • Theoretical lectures on the mechanisms of crop diversification (interactions in space and time) and its benefits and possible trade-offs (such a frequent legumes in crop rotation) • Visit to field experiment to see how crop diversification can be implemented at field level • Theoretical lectures on the mechanisms of crop diversification (interactions in space and time) and their benefits and possible trade-offs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discussion on risks associated to crop diversification based on students previous experiences, and on results obtained in DI • knowledge to schematize illustrations and later in the course to a real-world farm • risks of soil-borne pests and diseases, labour and machinery constraints, and marketing requirements constitute an integral part of understanding the current cropping system and the opportunities for alternative systems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Crop diversification is very complex and knowledge intensive. Students from diverse various educational background in Agroecology course found it difficult to understand the mechanisms and designing of crop diversification • There was question on whether it is easy to sow, harvest and sort crop mixtures (intercropping) • The mix of conceptual and partial knowledge was much appreciated: • “It was the course of this Mast of Organic Agriculture master most closely dealing with field knowledge and practice from a farmer's perspective - at last!” • “Helps to develop a knowledge base required to communicate with farmers and people that are active in practicing agriculture.”
		<p>Dynamic cropping system planning and management (crop sequence patterns to go beyond simple rotation)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation of alternative cropping systems as part of the farm strategy supported by spatio-temporal decision models (NDICEA, ROTAT, FarmDESIGN) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students apply the models and find information on alternative crop management options in the literature and through interviews with experts (farmers, teachers). The result is a series of alternative cropping systems and their performance in 	

				quantitative and qualitative terms	
		Functioning and set-up of machinery	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Challenges for machines to handle crop mixtures (sorting, cleaning) Focus was on strip cropping, which is meant to be a way to diversify cropping in a spatio-temporal manner using as much as possible current machinery. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Different types of machines for various operations were identified on-line. Using a protocol, students identified optimal strip widths based on requirements of the farm and on-farm availability of machinery. 	
Be able to	See the farm as a whole i.e., develop a systemic approach (problem analysis and strategic thinking)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Crop diversification, a lever at a territory level for larger issues: Example of protein autonomy in Western France Visit to four farms (some with more crop diversification than others) to perform SWOT and sustainability assessment using tool for agroecology performance evaluation (TAPE) developed by FAO. Throughout the course farms were considered as systems comprising soils, crops, animals and manure, with the farmer as the decision maker. This concept was reiterated regularly and the interconnections were emphasized. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Students took part to a Regional Conference on protein autonomy and Diversification (9/11/2021) organized by ESA and CA Pays de la Loire (France). They participated to different workshops during the conference. Students interviewed the farmers, assessed various farms, gave an oral presentation about the farms and presented a written report. Input were various interviews with the farmer during a 10- days on-farm stay. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of sufficient knowledge amongst the students on the cropping systems in Sweden made the exercise difficult for some students to design diversified/improved cropping system. Multi-criteria assessment tools require knowledge of social, environment and economic parameters and it's reported to be difficult for some students. Needed more time to learn and understand the cropping systems and tools. However, sustainability assessment tools such as LCA, TAPE and MASC were mentioned as interesting which students want to use in their thesis projects. Students liked the software tools at the cropping system and whole farm levels, which created structure and enabled asking directed questions. 	
	Develop diagnosis skills to evaluate and adjust the cropping system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assessment of crop diversification: inputs on multi criteria assessment of crop diversification for different actors, available tools and need of new tools Provided knowledge on sustainability assessment tools 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Live use of the excel tool 'global diversity' developed in DI to assess, compare different crop sequences Interactions with the tool designer 		

			<p>such as LCA, MASC and DEXi-PM to design and assess cropping systems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students were offered semi-quantitative methods of soil quality assessment, crop evaluation in time and space, and on-farm organization. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of impacts, improvements needed to better implement specific strategies • Students improved various reference arable and vegetable cropping systems by incorporating diversification strategies (such as intercropping, cover crops and lengthening of crop rotation) to increase the sustainability of reference system and presented in a plenary. • Students worked in groups on-farm and later in classroom on analysis of the current farm system using the quantitative and qualitative tools offered, and long-term data from the farm 	
Design under complex and uncertain context	Learn about	Value chain organization (actors, interactions, contractualization, price)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understanding of the complexity of the transition of agri food systems towards diversified systems (actors of the socio technical regime, interdependency of actors, self-reinforcement mechanisms...) • Identification of barriers at different levels (farm, value-chain, ...) • Lectures on concepts and theories of Gleissman's Five Level to transitions, Multi-level Perspective and Transition Management to understand lock-ins and find enablers for 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brainstorming on barriers and their classification • Identification of levers applicable to each actor of the value chain • Students discussed in groups to identify policies, interventions and programs that will help speed transition to more diversified food system. • During the on-farm period, students interview the farmer on the strategy and operational aspects around farm-external relations. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Some students felt that crop diversification seemed to suit better in small-scale farms than large-scale farms. • Some students also seemed to like/support the current food system (large-scale, long- value chain) and criticized the current rhetoric (small, diversified and local is better than the mainstream system) • Students were eager to apply a similar systems approach to other parts of the world, and wondered what additional problems they would face under new socio-technical contexts

			<p>transition to sustainable food systems</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The farm system is conceptualized as being a sub-system in the wider socio-technical system. Networks of exchange of knowledge, products, money and labour are highlighted. 		
		<p>On-farm experimentation (methods of experimentation and interpretation, dissemination)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Information pertaining to the design, implementation and some results of the DiverIMPACTS field experiment (FE) on diversifying organic cropping systems was shared During the first part of the course examples of on-farm experiences with crop diversification are shown from around the world. Drawing on a farmer master class on strip cropping real-world concerns and opportunities of farmers experimenting with strip cropping are provided. The farmer is interviewed on his experiences with experimenting with various new strategies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Listen and asked questions on the FE Listening and asking questions 	
	<p>Be able to</p>	<p>Search and contextualize knowledge for action by: Choose and manipulate digitalization tools to search for and disseminate relevant information</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Networking and exchanging using social/professional networks and platforms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Within the design-oriented part of the course, students search for information to develop challenging but plausible plans for the farm. They do this by searching internet (scientific and non-scientific) resources and calling experts. 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Some students were able to access existing networks; others needed to rely on internet. A richer source of informants is currently being put together

<p>Acquire the attitude to act within and have impact on the sociotechnical context</p>	<p>Be able to</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adapt his/her own attitude to address problems from different angles • interact and communicate in a multi-actor context • work as an innovation broker • take up a participative approach 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Role of scientist is questioned in the course: is a scientist someone who analyses phenomena and thus may end up understanding a great deal about a minor component of the system? What is the place of design-oriented science? • A module is dedicated to interviewing techniques 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Students from diverse educational background (agronomy, social science, economics, political science) interacted and shared their views/ pertaining to cropping systems design and assessment. It's a multi-actor participatory approach • Students discuss as part of the lectures the positions on analysis and design oriented scientific perspectives • Students practice on each other with interviewing, using peer review 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It can be challenging to work in groups (during the course and also relevant for multi-actor food systems) when members have different attitudes, aims and knowledge • During the course students were given the option to select their own team mates to work on re-design, having experienced working in teams during the on-farm analysis. This procedure worked well to arrive at stable teams in terms of skills and abilities.
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Conclusion and perspectives

Knowledge acquisition

Fundamental knowledge on crop diversification

Overall, teachers noticed a lack of knowledge amongst the students on the crops that can be grown in a diversified cropping system, and their agronomic details. This is a serious impediment to analysing and redesigning meaningful systems. This also confirms the need to bring up agronomic knowledge on crop diversification, its features and benefits/trade-offs. Further attention (time and contents) will then be brought to these concepts in all MSc courses dealing with crop diversification and agroecological transition.

Tools

Within the different three MSc programs, different tools and/or models either already existing (LCA, MASC, DEXi-PM) or developed within DI (global diversity) were mobilized for different purposes: assessing existing or proposed systems, help designing new cropping system, etc. In general, it was observed that:

- Students lacked knowledge on these tools. Thus it is relevant to present these tools and use them at this teaching program level. Students learn and put into practice simultaneously useful tools to design or assess cropping system. This increases the chances of dissemination and mobilization of such tools
- Using these tools is appreciated by students to design or assess cropping system
- Some tools/models, yet complex and difficult to grasp, encountered favourable reception by students with a projection to mobilize some of them in their future work which is very encouraging.

Skills acquisition

Course format

In the 3 experiences, courses were:

- based on exchange between students and between students and a (or more) farmer(s) and/or experts
- based on work groups
- based on a real-farm and situational setting

These formats were mostly appreciated by students and appeared to be favorable for training and learning of diversification concepts and cropping design and management.

Students were often asked to search for information by themselves, to discuss and share with each others and with a farmer, to analyze information and to discuss and present them. All this, allow students to develop communication and exchange skills necessary to evolve and be active in a multi-actor context. Searching for knowledge or discovering on-farm experimentation (through visits and testimonies) is also beneficial in a sense that it allows students to realize the diversity of ways to acquire information.

Overall feedbacks from students reinforce one of the main conclusions highlighted in DI regarding teaching strategies. It is mandatory to first of all make all students understand and master concepts of diversification and the resulting dynamics of change in farming practices. One of the students (SLU)

commented as such *“in one of the seminars we were asked to re-design a cropping system, but in reality I felt I still didn’t know how one could do that. I know the concept of crop rotations, but nothing about how they actually work, which is frustrating because I felt I couldn’t answer ‘how does intercropping work and why is it good’”*.

To fill this need, theoretical courses combined to practising and exchanging with stakeholders, including mainly farmers, appears to be the best pedagogical approach. Designing and assessing diversified systems can be facilitated by using interactive methods and innovative tools: on-farm situation, use of tools and models, group work and exchange.

To conclude, the experience led in the three MSc programs was overall satisfying and can be inspirational for other similar programs. The changes brought to these MSc programs will be renewed and reinforced in the coming years. Many researchers, teachers and PhD students perceive the importance of crop diversification to achieve various sustainability targets relating to agriculture. They are convinced that knowledge on it should be increased and disseminated. For example, a proposal for organizing an international PhD Course on crop diversification was submitted to the research school of SLU (decision still pending).